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Human Pose Estimation Using Depth-Wise Separable Convolutional Neural Networks

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KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

When it comes to dynamic human pose estimation, the process known as "identifying human joints in an image or video and determining their position in space" is used. This is done so that the dynamic position of the human body can be more accurately estimated and evaluated. This goal can be achieved by applying various computer vision strategies used in a number of industries such as gaming, robotics training, and animation. In this article, we propose a method for dynamic human pose estimation using convolutional neural networks (CNN). This method will soon be used as a form of physical therapy rehabilitation that can be performed in a remote setting. By making an assessment of the patient's postures, the physical therapist can determine whether or not the patient is performing the assigned exercises correctly. With this method, the physiotherapist can correctly adapt the therapy sessions to the progress that the patient is making in the recovery process.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the importance of technology as a factor in improving people's lives, especially in the field of medicine, has increased. This increase is due to the fact that technological advancements have facilitated the diagnosis and treatment of various diseases and injuries. This trend is likely to continue into the future; in particular, the development of immersive therapeutic applications, programs for the treatment of various diseases and injuries, has been facilitated by virtual reality that has paved the way for the development of such applications. These applications aim to increase accuracy of therapeutic interventions and reduce the severity of a variety of injuries and illnesses and associated symptoms by addressing them more precisely and in a targeted fashion. Thanks to the development of these mobile applications, patients now have access to information, rehabilitation and different types of treatment remotely.

This paper's objective is to discuss progress toward the development of systems capable of guiding physiotherapy-related tasks on behalf of patients undergoing treatment in the comfort of their own homes. This system is based on virtual reality and its objective is to lessen the risk of injury to patients executing prescribed exercises incorrectly at home by providing them with feedback and instruction as they execute the exercises. These patients could benefit from using the system that allows them to continue with their normal day-to-day activities.

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Another purpose of this paper is to apply CNN to provide estimates of the human poses for a single individual. One of the reasons that these networks are so successful is that their organizational framework is comparable to that of a human's brain. Convolutional neural networks, more commonly known as CNNs, have swiftly risen to prominence as the method of choice for addressing issues related to image classification. This is due, in part, to the high degree of accuracy that CNN possesses. In a wide variety of object recognition tasks, CNNs have demonstrated astonishing levels of performance; this is due to the fact that network structures enable them to extract multiple levels of information from a single image.

2. BACKGROUND

Since 2014, and especially during the past six years, the use of and interest in Human Pose Estimation (HPE) has expanded, primarily as a result of the introduction of Deep Learning. From the initial rudimentary neural networks to today's complicated CNNs have significantly progressed. The use of filters to obtain lines, edges, silhouettes, and other distinctive characteristics of the elements contained in an image, as well as the ability to provide data to a system that can learn certain characteristics and then detect them when presented with a similar situation, have prompted a turning point (Badiola-Bengoa & Mendez-Zorrilla, 2021).

Typically, applications of pose estimation to rehabilitation following injury or surgery include the use of techniques to monitor an individual's return to normal movement patterns and to direct the motion of rehabilitation technology that is designed to interface with the patient. Pose estimation approaches have been utilized to evaluate and assess a patient's range of motion and movement during functional activities. Particular attention has been placed on using pose estimation to track rehabilitation progress outside of the clinic, such as at home or on the athletic field. In addition, numerous technologies have been created to actively interact with patients in order to either support their movement during therapy or offer a mechanical stimulus to improve rehabilitation outcomes. These technologies are usually referred to as rehabilitation robotics; methodologies utilizing pose estimation to guide the movement of these systems have been developed (Stenum et al., 2021).

The versatility of the technology, which is one of the most important aspects that contribute to its usefulness, has numerous applications within the optimization of human performance and safety, including injury risk assessment, rehabilitation, and performance enhancement. This application space typically involves an instructor, such as a coach, a trainer, or a clinician, who assesses an individual's movement patterns to determine whether the individual is for pathomechanical injury or delayed recovery. Two-dimensional pose estimation techniques, for instance, have been used to create proof-of-concept screening technologies that detect abnormal gait patterns during walking and running, fall detection, abnormal movements that are indicative of injury risk in manual labor work environments, and risk of sports-related injury, such as anterior cruciate ligament rupture. Post-injury analysis has primarily focused on sports performance applications and mechanisms of injury, with the end goal of developing strategies to reduce injury risk and restore normal mechanics, speed, strength and endurance to injured area (Stenum et al., 2021).

Human Pose Estimation can be carried out in a variety of ways; that can be broken down into two broad categories: techniques that begin at the top and work their way down, and strategies that begin at the bottom and work their way up the kinetic chain. When various strategies are categorized, they can be placed into either of these two categories depending on how they are ordered according to the individual qualities that they possess. Bottom-up algorithms, for instance, begin by estimating the position of each joint in the body (Cao et al., 2019; Pishchulin et al., 2016; Papandreou et al., 2018; Ning et al., 2017; Newell et al., 2017); this stage is the first step of the process. Once this stage is

completed, algorithms proceed to the next stage, whereby the estimated joint positions are combined into a single pose. Once this stage is completed, the algorithms move to the next stage. On the other hand, top-down procedures (Fang et al., 2017; Moon et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2018; He et al., 2018) begin by identifying the person, and then determining the body joints of that person within the bounding boxes that have been identified.

3. WHAT IS POSE ESTIMATION?

Pose estimation is an artificial intelligence technology that analyzes images using machine learning algorithms. The idea is that neural network-based algorithms perform human pose recognition and body movement tracking in real time using a camera. The main applications of pose estimation technologies are as follows (Kalinin, 2021):

3.1 Fitness

When we think of automatic pose detection, the first things that come to mind are fitness, physique, and range of motion. Many startups are investigating AI capabilities for pose recognition. This technology enabled them to develop AI-powered personal trainers that assess how customers perform exercises and whether they require assistance in correcting their body position. Such fitness apps democratize personal coaching services by:

- lowering the cost of having a one-to-one professional trainer;
- lowering the risk of injury.

3.2 Physical Therapy

Another emerging trend in pose estimation is the development of physical therapy apps that detect body postures and provide users with feedback on specific physical exercises. Again, the benefits are:

- lower costs of care due to no or minimal physical therapist involvement;
- improved health outcomes for users;
- the ease of at-home exercise.

3.3 Entertainment

Pose detection software can also assist in the replacement of costly motion capture systems used in film and video game production. In video games, movement recognition can help create more immersive experiences. KINECT, for example, can use IR sensors to track the player's movements and relay them to its virtual avatar's actions. The benefits include:

- lower film production costs;
- improved user engagement.

3.4 Robotics

Another application of this computer vision technology is the control of robots. The rigid logic and movements of robots are replaced in this case by pose detection and estimation algorithms that allow for more flexible response. Positive features include:

- very little recalibration;
- rapid adaptation to a wide range of environments.

4. HOW DOES POSE ESTIMATION WORK?

The basic idea behind pose estimation is to use machine learning algorithms, running on convolutional neural networks, to process RGB (aka normal, regular) or infrared (IR) images (Kalinin, 2021). Because many mobile devices and laptops have built-in cameras, RGB image-based pose detection is easier to implement than IR. Infrared images can be captured using KINECT and RealSense infrared cameras.

4.1 Skeleton Recognition

The neural network tracks the human body's major joints (e.g., knees, elbows, and feet) and then reconstructs a human skeleton and its movements based on its relative position and proximity of adjacent structures. Joint and corresponding body part positions correspond to various postures.

4.2 Bottom-Up and Top-Down Approaches

Pose recognition algorithms first identify a human when using the top-down approach. Following that, each human object is placed in a virtual box, and posture is assessed by tracking key anatomical points within the box. In the bottom-up approach, joints are organized into hierarchies and, eventually, skeletons; this leads to body position recognition and modeling.

4.3 Body Model

Before poses can be identified, CNNs require a well-defined body model. Simple kinematic body models have 13 to 30 points, whereas more detailed body models—mesh models—can have hundreds or thousands of points.

4.4 Pre- and Post-Processing

Proper pose estimation also necessitates image pre- and post-processing. Pre-processing may include removing the image's background and adding body contours (placing each recognized person in a box); geometry analysis is used in post-processing! Based on the findings, a fitness app with an AI assistant can advise users on how to improve their workouts.

4.5 Multi-Person vs. Singular-Person Pose Estimation

Multi-person pose detection is more difficult than single-person pose detection because a neural network must first successfully identify each person before evaluating and reconstructing his or her posture. Furthermore, people may block each other's views and interact in ways that make body recognition extremely difficult.

4.6 2D vs. 3D Pose Detection

Pose detection algorithms can perform 2D or 3D pose estimation. They estimate poses in an image in 2D and predict poses in an actual spatial arrangement in 3D. 3D pose recognition is more difficult because the background scene and lighting conditions must be considered and adjusted for optimal capture.

4.7 Images vs. Video

Pose detection from single images has already been established. The only difference between pose estimation from video and pose estimation from software is that software must decompile a video into a

series of images; these images are then subjected to pose recognition processing. Pose estimation in videos has advantages because neural networks can see gradual or precise changes in posture and identify frames where specific body parts are visible (as opposed to frames with occluded body parts).

5. POSE ESTIMATION TOOLS

Pose estimations in 2D and 3D approaches require different toolsets.

5.1 Pose Estimation in 2D

Google has already developed specialized neural network architectures designed specifically for 2D pose estimation (see PoseNet below).

5.1.1 *PoseNet*

PoseNet is available from Google in two variants: single-pose detection and multiple-pose estimation. The PoseNet model works by taking an image from a camera as input and resizing it so that the model can run it. The model's next step is to output information on 16 body parts and compile them into a skeleton. Further, the model provides a confidence score for each pose, which can be thresholded to eliminate poses where the system is unsure about how to classify them.

5.2 Pose Estimation in 3D

Kinect or RealSense cameras are used to estimate 3D poses. They both have advantages and disadvantages.

5.2.1 *Kinect*

Kinect is a low-cost Microsoft camera for movement analysis that includes a depth sensor that captures depth data based on a video feed of infrared images. An Azure Kinect Developer Kit is required for the development. It includes hardware (the camera) and two Software Development Kits (SDK) for working with the depth sensor and body tracking algorithms. After installing the necessary libraries and prerequisites, the code from GitHub can be pulled and the pose estimation app can be developed. The demos in the GitHub repository, among other things, display information about joints by tracking body orientation and depth.

Among the advantages of Kinect are:

- the ability to estimate pose depth over a wide range (up to 5 meters)
- The body tracking algorithm is pre-trained on a large dataset and can output up to 30 frames per second.

5.2.2 *RealSense*

Alternatively, Intel's RealSense camera can be used. RealSense offers many of the same advantages as Kinect in terms of capturing high-resolution depth and color information, but at a faster rate — 90 frames per second. As a result, the output models move more smoothly. RealSense offers more than enough in terms of development. Their SDK, which is available on GitHub, includes a viewer, a depth quality tool, debugging tools, and many types of wrappers for integration with third-party libraries. Aside from that, they provide a standalone skeleton tracking SDK, with one drawback: it is not free! Positive features include:

- cross-platform (supports multiple language interfaces);
- No specialized hardware, such as a Graphics Processing Unit (GPU), is required to track multiple people.

6. METHODOLOGY

The first step in determining an object's pose involved loading an image into a tensor flow session and using a model weight to represent the object. Following that, the process of estimating an object's pose started. This session also included an architecture of a neural network, which was used to determine how the layers of the network were to be organized, as well as the weights that were saved during the processing of the pre-trained model.

Five crucial components made up the open pose pipeline, all of which collaborated to form the entire system. An algorithm generated a two-dimensional map of important anatomical locations for an individual based on the input image and its specific dimensions of width and height. This image represented the individual who was depicted in the input image. In addition, the width and height of the input image were specified. The system made use of a feedback network to estimate the 2D confidence maps of the body parts, which were denoted by the letter S. Additionally, the system made use of a feedback network to estimate the 2D vector fields that encoded the body parts, which were denoted by the letter L.

A J map of confidence was provided for every component in the set $s = "S_1, S_2... S_J,"$, as shown below:

$$S_j \in \mathbb{R}^{w \times h}, j \in \{1 \dots J\} \quad (1)$$

Every item in the set $L = L_1, L_2, L_C$ was represented by one C vector field; the fields were denoted by:

$$L_c \in \mathbb{R}^{w \times h \times 2}, c \in \{1 \dots C\} \quad (2)$$

In the end, greedy inferences were used to research trust maps and Part Affinity Fields (PAFs) so that 2D skeletons of the people in the input image could be made.

After the input image had been processed using the VGG-19 algorithm, it was then possible to obtain the F-maps. Following this, the two divisions then yielded the PAFs and the confidence maps, simultaneously.

As shown in Figure 1, the architecture was composed of two phases; each phase had two branches. The beige branches developed the confidence maps for each succeeding phase, while the blue branches prepared the PAFs for each phase. When the finished products were combined with the inputs, they yielded a single output. The forecast was modified at every stage to account for every phase's specific loss value; this was done because the process consisted of several stages, as well as intermediate monitoring stages. In the context of this research, the loaded graph was broken down into seven different steps.

Figure 1. Architecture of the 2D Pose Estimation Model

A group of confidence maps, denoted by S_1 , and a set of PAFs, denoted by L_1 , were produced during the first stage of the process. The connection between the two stages is shown below:

$$S_1 = p_1(F) \tag{3}$$

$$L_1 = \phi^1(F) \tag{4}$$

The equations shown below were used to figure out S_t and L_t for the next phase.

$$S_t = p^t(F, S^{(t-1)}, L^{(t-1)}) \quad \forall t \geq 2 \tag{5}$$

$$L_t = \phi^t(F, S^{(t-1)}, L^{(t-1)}) \quad \forall t \geq 2 \tag{6}$$

One L_2 loss function was applied to each branch. The following equations provide an explanation of how the loss function operates when both branches are in stage t (Cao et al., 2019):

$$f_s^t = \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_p W(p) \cdot \|S_j^t(p) - S_j^*(p)\|_2^2 \tag{7}$$

$$f_l^t = \sum_{c=1}^C \sum_p W(p) \cdot \|L_c^t(p) - L_c^*(p)\|_2^2 \tag{8}$$

where S_j^* is the confidence map, L_c^* is the ground truth part affinity vector field, and W is a binary mask, with $W(p) = 0$. The primary function was broken down into the following categories:

$$f = \sum_{t=1}^T (f_s^t + f_l^t) \tag{9}$$

A subset of CNNs, known as depth-wise separable convolutional neural networks (DS-CNN), was applied for image processing. This process was broken down into five steps, see Figure 2.

Figure 2. Pose Estimation Using the DS-CNN Process

The layers consisted of the following components:

- 1) **Depth-wise Convolution:** This method applies a convolution to only one channel at a time, in contrast to the standard CNN method, which applies the convolution to all of the channels at the same time. The depth of the convolution is determined by the number of channels in the image. This allows for a greater overall reduction in the complexity of calculations.
- 2) **Pointwise:** In this step, one combines the outputs of the depth-wise convolution into a single result by applying a 1 x 1 convolution. This step is called "pointwise" convolution. This operation is carried out immediately after the depth-wise convolution is completed.
- 3) **Batch Norm:** The goal of this operation is to hasten the process of training while simultaneously lowering the risk of overfitting, as a consequence of the regularization process. This is accomplished through the use of a batching technique. This normalization strategy is implemented at the level of individual batches of data, as opposed to being applied to the entire data set, in order to save time.
- 4) **The Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU)** is a type of linear function that always returns a positive value regardless of the value given as input. This characteristic sets it apart from the various other types of linear functions. If the input is greater than zero, then the output will also be greater than zero; if not, it will be set at zero. If the input is zero, then the output will always be zero. However, if the input is greater than some predetermined limit, then there is a linear relationship between the independent variable and the input: $f(x) = 0$ if x is less than zero, and x if x is equal to or more than zero.

$$f(x) = 0 \text{ if } x < 0, \text{ and } x \text{ if } x \geq 0 \quad (10)$$

- 5) **Pooling:** The pooling layers of the feature map provide a summary of the features that can be discovered in a particular region of the feature map. One of the goals of the pooling layers is to cut down on the number of parameters that need to be learned.

7. EXPERIMENTS

7.1 2D Pose Estimation

As a first input, we started by displaying an image at the start of the session. A total of about 0.2 seconds of time was required to arrive at a rough estimate of the 2D pose. Next, we provided a video as a contribution to the process that was to be followed. To get a 2D pose estimate, it took an average of 0.2 seconds to 0.03 seconds. The result obtained in both of these circumstances is shown in Figure 3, which is a skeleton with landmarks that connect the significant points of the human body. This result was achieved in all the different scenarios that were studied.

Figure 3. 2D Pose Estimation of an Avatar in an Image Input

7.2 3D Pose Estimation

During this experiment, we went from a two-dimensional to a three-dimensional process and were responsible for distributing data across sockets. This procedure took approximately 0.7 seconds, with a margin of error of 0.1 seconds on either side of the estimate. The outcome of this scenario was determined by the degree to which a single image was repeated over multiple frames. If the image was already present in the previous frame, the procedure took much less time to complete because the data had already been roughly calculated. If the image was not already present, the procedure took the same time to complete. The result of this process is presented in "Figure 4," whereby the sent array had an estimated Z coordinate, in addition to the X and Y coordinates that were already there.

Figure 4. Incorrect 2D Pose Estimation

7.3 Pose estimation under different situations

Estimating a person's posture is a difficult task. Therefore, it was of the utmost necessity to test our method under a variety of variables and situations. Due to the fact that this technique is intended for physiotherapy exercises involving numerous complex movements, the information needed to be exact.

- 1) **Front Body View:** This process provided a view of the front body, along with the number of joints that were detected. The results are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Input vs. Result of the Pose Estimation of a Front Body View Image

- 2) **View of the Body from the Side:** This approach gave a perspective of the body from the side, along with the number of joints that were detected. The results are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Input vs. Result of the Pose Estimation of Side Body View Image

- 3) **Pose Estimation for Multiple People:** This process provided a view of pose estimation for multiple people, along with the number of joints that were detected. The results are presented in Figures 7 and 8.

Figure 7. Input vs. Result of the Pose Estimation of a Multi-Person View Image

Figure 8. Input vs. Result of the Pose Estimation of a Multi-Person View Image

- 4) **Angled Body View:** This approach gave a perspective of pose estimation for an angled body, along with the number of joints that were detected. The results are presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Input vs. Result of the Pose Estimation of an Angled Body View Image

- 5) **The Gaussian blur effect:** A gaussian blur effect was applied to an image to determine how well the system worked. The results are presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Input vs. Result of the Pose Estimation of a Blurry Image

- 6) **The Gaussian noise effect:** A gaussian noise effect was applied to an image to determine how well the system worked. The amount of noise, as well as the strength of the noise, were both adjusted to a value of 30 pixels. The projected number of joints and poses decreased when the noise values were greater than or equal to 30 pixels. When a significant number of noise pixels existed, the process of pose estimation did begin, and consequently no results were displayed. The results are presented in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Input vs. Result of the Pose Estimation of a Noisy Image

The results of the different scenarios under study are presented table 1.

Table 1. Pose Estimation for the Different Scenarios

<i>Scenario Number</i>	<i>Total Number of people</i>	<i>Estimated joints</i>	<i>Incorrect Key Points</i>	<i>Missing Joints</i>	<i>Processing time (seconds)</i>
Scenario 1	1	17	0	0	0.45
Scenario 2	1	14	2	3	0.47
Scenario 3 (1)	5	0-8-0-7-11	0	17-9-17-10-6	0.8
Scenario 3 (2)	4	17-17-17-17	0	0	0.65
Scenario 4	1	9	0	8	0.5
Scenario 5	1	17	0	0	0.45
Scenario 6	1	9	0	8	0.48

8. ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

When using the method described in this paper to determine someone's pose, the viewing angle is crucial. This has an impact on how the position is perceived. The perspective of the observer determines the angle of the scene; previous studies from hypothetical circumstances support this claim. Table 1 above omits crucial information, which contributes to misjudging the position. This is illustrated by how the location can be misjudged if certain body parts are hidden.

When an image exhibited a high degree of noise, the algorithm produced no data or results. The noise wiped out virtually every pixel in the image, thus removing many crucial body parts. When it comes to the degree of precision that an estimate can achieve once presented, the quality of the information provided plays a decisive role. Despite the limitations, the method we used was able to accurately predict the position of a substantial fraction of key points in the vast majority of cases. On the other hand, the algorithm was unable to reliably predict the location of specific joints because it could not identify them in the input image.

9. CONCLUSION AND FURTHER RESEARCH SUGGESTIONS

In this paper, we have introduced a method for implementing depth-wise separable convolution for pose estimation. Due to this convolution, depth information was differentiated from posed information, despite the fact that it struggled to deliver a result under certain conditions, such as when the angle of view is challenging or when the quality of the input is low. Based on the results of the tests, the method described in this paper can be used to estimate the pose of one person or many people.

As we move forward with this project, one of the key concerns will be to ensure that the proposed method is precise and efficient. We see great prospects for the continuous maturity and validation of the proposed method to provide strong complements or alternatives to subjective visual motor assessments and to increase the accessibility of measurement of movement kinematics by removing long-standing restrictions. The capacity to acquire quantitative, whole-body kinematics using a household device could significantly reduce reliance on inaccessible or data-limited older approaches, such as pricey research-grade motion capture equipment or wearable devices.

We see great promise for this technology applied to understanding injury mechanisms and rehabilitation, as well as occupational ergonomic analysis to identify and eliminate or reduce risk factors for work-related musculoskeletal injury. We believe that occupational safety and ergonomic professionals should embrace new tools and technologies to protect workers and prevent injury, pain, suffering, and associated losses.

The endeavor conducted in this study for dynamic human position assessment via convolutional neural networks (CNN) could be employed as a remote-accessible type of physical therapy rehabilitation. By looking at the patient's posture, the physical therapist can tell if the patient is doing his or her exercises in the right way.

Using the so-called immersive technologies, which have demonstrated promise in a variety of therapeutic fields, the endeavor described in this paper seeks to provide a solution to physiotherapy problems. The immersive environment in which the exercises would take place is a replica of the physiotherapist's office. This scenario is formed by a physiotherapist-installed network of multimedia sensors that would collect data from the clinic. In order to achieve the desired outcomes, the training session will be led by an avatar representing the physiotherapist, who will execute the identical exercises in real time. This method increases the patient's involvement with the physical therapist and

decreases the likelihood of improper training execution. Augmented reality will be added to this interface to help keep the patient safe and guide him or her toward more useful activities.

In addition, we intend to establish a dashboard for the physical therapist that will enable him or her to diagnose patients and alter their exercises depending on ongoing developments and the outcomes of past office visits. However, this interactive simulation that makes use of virtual reality and augmented reality technologies does not replace actual visits to the physical therapist's office; rather, it serves as a supplement to lower the chance of rehabilitation failure. The instrument is designed to be adaptive and scalable in order to provide professional development-related exercises, and can be used in hospitals for rehabilitation following a surgery.

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